

1 **An expression screen to identify genes important for trastuzumab resistance: Lrrc37a4p.**

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6 We measured total transcription by RNA-sequencing in patients sensitive or resistant to treatment with
7 trastuzumab for HER2+ breast cancer for discovery of genes that confer or support resistance to
8 HER2-targeted therapies in humans. In this manuscript we describe identification of Lrrc37a4p as a
9 candidate gene product of the trastuzumab resistance gene expression signature.

10 Citations

11 1. Wang, H., Makowski, C., Zhang, Y., Qi, A., Kaufmann, T., Smeland, O.B., Fiecas, M., Yang, J.,
12 Visscher, P.M. and Chen, C.H., 2023. Chromosomal inversion polymorphisms shape human brain
13 morphology. Cell reports, 42(8).